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THE UNITED NILGIRI TEA ESTATES COMPANY LTD, NILGIRIS – A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

The United Nilgiri Tea Estates Company Ltd. is one of the earliest and oldest plantations in the Nilgiris (known as South India's Darjeeling) with estates at Chamraj, Allada Valley, Devabetta and Korakundah. The estates are located at 8000 ft above MSL and produce some of the finest orthodox, black, green and decaffeinated teas. Sir Robert Stanes, a young lad from England landed on the shores of Madras and went onto find UNITEA in the year 1922. The total number of employees is 1078. It has been 94 years of energetic growth, experience and excellence. Ms. Mallika Srinivasan is the current Chairman and CEO of UNITEA. The popular brands of UNITEA are Chamraj Tea, and Korakundah Tea.

VISION: Consistent improvement in both quality and quantity of production of all varieties of teas. To be a world leader in the export of high grown teas.

VALUES: These values govern their everyday actions in their professional and personal lives. They are *Quality*– Deliver quality products adhering to the highest standards, *People* –Value our people, our customers and shareholders, *Community*–Be accountable citizens in the communities we live and work in, *Integrity*–Uphold high ethical standards in all our actions, *Environment* – To be loyal stewards of our planet, *Transparency and Accountability* – Transparent in our actions and firm in delivering our commitments.

ACHIEVEMENTS: Over the past 94 years UNITEA has been the forerunner in many areas. It has set trends and broken ground for others to follow. To name a few: First “South Indian Tea” to command the price of Rs.1000/- per kg, First producer of Organic tea in India (since 1994), First amongst plantations to achieve ISO 9002 certification (1997), Built certification guidelines for Fairtrade for tea plantations and is one of the first estates to be certified (1994).

AWARDS: Winner of The Golden Leaf Award 2005 – 2016, Winner of World Tea Championship Award for Chamraj – 2008, Winner of Great Taste Awards – UK for Chamraj & Korakundah Tea – 2012 – 2014, Korakundah Tea Garden is the highest tea garden in the World – Elite World Record.

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: The Company has been taking initiatives and contributing to many social causes such as education to the children of the villages around the estate through the running of two well established schools, health-care through a well established hospital, running a home for orphan children besides environment protection.

EFFICIENCY: UNITEA takes great pride in leading the plantations in terms of energy efficiency and reduced carbon footprint. All of UNITEA's water is from natural spring sources. Water is harvested from these springs without pumping and hence protecting the water table for posterity. Rainwater harvesting is another diligent focus area. Management has adopted 5S and Quality control mechanism.

COMMITMENT TO QUALITY: Quality check at each stage of production and right up to point of shipment is part of the routine. ISO 9001:2008, ISO 14001: 2004, ISO 22000: 2005, Tea Tasting is the main and most important method of quality check. There is no mechanical device used for tea tasting. It has to be manually done by experts.

LABOUR WELFARE SCHEMES: UNITEA welfare schemes are unique and first amongst plantations: Healthcare and Health Insurance (inclusive of medicines), Education for the Employees Children, Retirement Housing Scheme, Pension Scheme, Cooking Gas, Subsidized Electricity, Physical Fitness – State of the art gymnasium at the disposal of UNITEA employees.

Pension scheme: The Pension Scheme is one of the major welfare projects initiated in the year 1997. A corpus fund has been created and the pension is being paid out of the interest accrued. Salient features of the welfare fund are, No contribution is made towards this fund by the workers. Pension is met purely from the interest earned, Workers who have completed 30 years of service are eligible to receive Rs.1,500/- per month, and those between 20 and 30 years of service are eligible to receive Rs.1,000/- per month (beginning at the retirement age of 58 years), Pension is disbursed for 10 years from the retirement age of 58 years.

Retirement housing scheme: 90% of UNITEA's workforce is from the plains, migrating to the estates in search of work. Once they are part of the plantation, their lives are woven with the estates for a long time to come. UNITEA worked with the employees and devised the retirement housing scheme – that provides for the workers towards their housing dreams on retirement. Every year, the employee sets aside a portion of his/her earnings, and UNITEA contributes towards the same to create the retirement housing fund. This gives the employees to retire with dignity to his / her home at the end of a long fulfilling career.

RETENTION STRATEGY: UNITEA, follows a unique policy to retain its employees. The company provides Rs.10000 per employee if he / she maintain a minimum attendance of 240 days. And also provides an attractive 20% bonus to its employees. Employees rarely leave the company.

ERP: Chamraj Tea Estate Management System (TEAMS) is designed to computerize the complete operation and management of a Tea estate. The system handles all activities such as production, maintenance of estates, inventory, and accounting of sales, purchase and payroll of various division staff. It reports analysis based upon the yield, production and MIS for decision making by the top management. It has secure user friendly interface. It incorporates the current computer technologies which will serve the needs of the tea estate for at least 10 years.

CONCLUSION: Committed employees are the main source of strength for the organization. The company takes maximum care to ensure stability of employment and strives to improve working conditions and there exists a good employer – employee relationship. The Company believes that “Safety of the employees comes first”. At every step of the production, rigorous quality checks are performed right from the raw materials to the finished goods. The product strategy of UNITEA is based on developing new innovative flavours to become a pioneer in tea industry. The company is working on improving its strategies to increase its brand value.